

Maximum Likelihood Estimation and Likelihood Ratio test revisited

Abstract

Maximum likelihood Estimation is an important aspect of frequentist approach which was introduced by RA Fisher [1]. Maximum Likelihood estimation method helps us to find the estimator for the unknown population parameter. There are other methods of estimation also available such as Least Square Estimation and Bayesian Estimation methods but Maximum Likelihood Estimation is the widely used method to estimate the parameters. This paper provides an overview of Maximum Likelihood Method with example to calculate a Maximum Likelihood Estimator from a sample data set.

Keywords: Maximum Likelihood Estimation; parametric; likelihood; likelihood ratio; likelihood ratio test; chi square;

Full paper can be accessed at

www.vinaitheerthan.com/MLE.PHP